

LIBERALIZATION OF ECONOMIC RELATIONS IN AGRICULTURE

Khakimova Guzal Akbar qizi

Namangan engineering – construction institute, student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12903874>

Abstract: the article scientifically analyzes the directions of liberalization of economic relations in agriculture as a factor in achieving food security.

Key words: agriculture, food security, frugality, efficiency, employment, homestead farming, export.

Currently, the problems observed in the world economy are manifested in connection with the implementation of economic processes in agriculture. Extensive measures are being taken to ensure the rapid development of agriculture in Uzbekistan, the agrarian sector is provided with appropriate financial resources, and the financial support of agrarian development is consistently continued. The agrarian reforms carried out in Uzbekistan are aimed at ensuring the rapid growth of the sector, increasing the employment and well-being of the rural population. Therefore, " Uzbekistan - market reforms in the agrarian sector implemented according to the 2030 strategy In addition to setting long-term fundamental goals, it also includes determining the means and ways to achieve these goals. Reforms are aimed at moving agricultural production to the basis of modern technologies and constantly increasing its efficiency, along with the expansion of economic freedoms.

The consistent expansion of the scope of free market relations in the agricultural sector ensures that the activities of the sector are primarily focused on the goals of ensuring the country's food security. This is in harmony with various aspects of the independent movement of the national economy in the current conditions (economic security, financial security, food security, energy security, supply of medicines and medical equipment, saving jobs, etc.). Although the importance of external resources (material, financial, scientific, etc.) should not be denied in the conditions of the global crisis, it is also evident that each country has to solve its problems first of all with its own forces.

In the conditions of market relations, when economic entities act independently, the importance of financial support from the state is becoming extremely important. In Uzbekistan, the state's anti-crisis measures are focused on direct and indirect financial support of economic entities. These include reducing the tax burden, simplifying the terms and conditions of bank lending, expanding the resource base of bank lending.

Currently, the role of food export has increased. Also, not only nutritional and energetic properties of food products, but also their value in terms of impact on human immunity are being taken into consideration. These factors open up new opportunities for the export of fruits and vegetables, opening the way to large markets for producers. New promising directions of export are developing. For example, in 9 months of 2020, 8720 tons of canned fruits and vegetables worth 9365 thousand US dollars were exported from our country. This was 3,607.4 tons more than in the corresponding period of 2019. In 2022 and 2023, the export of agricultural food products will reach 1 bln. is more than USD and has a steady growth trend. The geography and assortment of exports is expanding.

Opportunities for agricultural development in Uzbekistan can be seen in the example of horticulture, one of its traditional industries. Fruit and grape growing has a special place in ensuring the well-being of the population and food security of the country. The existing conditions for the development of horticulture in Uzbekistan allow the production of the industry's products in quantities that are sufficient to meet the domestic needs of the country. It is also possible to achieve high competitiveness of the product for export. Because the natural and climatic conditions of our country: a) the vegetation period lasts long enough; b) the effective temperature sum is sufficiently large (days when the average daily soil temperature is above +10); c) land resources and natural soil fertility; g) natural solar radiation background; d) amount of natural precipitation; e) average date of winter frost; j) water resources contribute to the high nutritional value of the product. The labor potential of horticulture is: a) the number of able-bodied population; b) the general level of knowledge and skills of the workforce; c) historically formed national traditions of respect for work in horticulture of fruit, vegetable and grape cultivation; g) is being formed on the basis of factors such as opportunities for training personnel capable of using modern technologies for horticulture (vocational education system).

Economic and organizational conditions supporting the development of horticulture:

- a) that the traditions of fruit and grape growing and agrotechnical culture and skills are preserved in households;
- b) establishment of farms specializing in horticulture, fruit and vegetable and grape growing; c) that the operating farms are more oriented towards fruit and grape cultivation;

g) processes of agro-industry integration are observed in horticulture (many farms are starting to process their own products);

d) positive trends observed in the introduction of new technologies to horticulture;

e) volume of horticulture lending by commercial banks is rapidly increasing;

j) tax system encouraging the development of horticulture; z) state financing of horticulture production infrastructure;

i) market infrastructure serving the sale of horticultural products;

k) availability of domestic demand for horticultural products and demand outside the country;

l) horticulture products are characterized by their competitiveness in terms of cost and consumer characteristics.

Therefore, the concept of agricultural development in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 envisages the liberalization of the sector and the strengthening of food orientation. In 2020, 86 clusters and 125 cooperatives were established in our country to accelerate the processes of agro-industry integration in the fruit and vegetable network. Their activity should serve to strengthen the material interest of producers in the production of food products that are competitive and in demand in foreign markets. Clusters and cooperatives should not only sell the product, but also organize its storage and processing. As a result, an added value chain is formed and socio-economic efficiency is achieved.

Market reforms in the agrarian sector are focused on ensuring the well-being of the rural population and reducing poverty in the conditions of the coronavirus pandemic. In this regard, the financial support of households by the state gives both economic and social results. In Uzbekistan, the number of personal auxiliary households is 4.5 million, and they have 435 thousand hectares of land at their disposal. On April 15, 2020, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan made a decision on the effective use of farm plots and the systematic organization of planting works. 300 billion of the state budget will be allocated to support them in 2020. 100 billion soum funds and 100 bln. bank loans are allocated. In addition, the state will allocate 600 billion to build light construction greenhouses for the population. sent soum .

In general, the role of animal husbandry in the agriculture of our country is increasing, and this is primarily due to the increase in the well-being of the population. For example, on the eve of independence, the annual consumption of

meat and meat products per capita was 15 kilograms, but now this figure is 3 times higher. Meat is taking an increasingly important place in the population's diet. This will affect market demand, and demand will not affect prices. The root of the problem lies in the fodder base of livestock breeding. Therefore, in our opinion, it is time to abandon the residual principle in allocating land for cattle breeding, and allocate highly productive land to the network. Another important direction is the sharp expansion of alfalfa areas. Because the feed units supplied by bedopa are 1.5 times more compared to other crops, and the cost is 3-4 times cheaper. It is necessary to restore the network that was abandoned due to the monopoly of cotton. We believe that the export of alfalfa concentrate can also be launched.

The most important production resource in agriculture is land, and maintaining its productivity will always be a priority. Today, worldwide, soil fertility is decreasing year by year, which has a negative impact on productivity and product quality. At the moment, there is a need to introduce an acceptable "NPK" system based on a thorough analysis of the soil composition in each plot, and cotton-grain-alfalfa rotation on 10-15 percent of the fields every year. As a result, it is possible to reduce the demand for mineral fertilizers due to the improvement of the physical properties of the soil, and water resources are also saved. In this way, 33-35 thousand tons of seeds will be saved per year, the price of grain will decrease, and it will be possible to increase productivity by 8-10%.

Farming occupies a special place in the agriculture of Uzbekistan and in ensuring the country's food security. 65-70 percent of agricultural products are grown on farms and estates. At the moment, the organization of wide application of new effective technologies and developments related to agriculture at the level of neighborhoods, households and farms has not been established.

Therefore, first of all, it is necessary to increase the scope, reliability and promotion of agricultural research by conducting experiments and research at the neighborhood, household and farm level. 5.5 million inhabitants in 2023 509 thousand hectares of crops in his estate husbands was available . Main from products potatoes, tomatoes, cabbage and 70-75 % of leeks , 65 % of onions , 40 % of carrots population garden and a farmer farms contribution right is coming

Currently, the issues of agricultural development and ensuring food security of the country are set wider and deeper and include:

- increasing the production of the most important products in stable volumes;

- maintaining and strengthening competitiveness of products in domestic and foreign markets, export orientation;
- increase production efficiency based on innovative development (new technologies and agrotechnics, variety replacement, introduction of production of clean organic products, water and energy saving, high culture of farming);
- coordination of agricultural development with environmental requirements.

The problems of developing agriculture based on market principles can be described as follows. It is necessary to bring the material and technical support of the network to the level of modern requirements. Because: a) lack of specialized equipment; b) that the level of use of advanced agricultural technology is low; c) failure to satisfy the demand for chemicals and mineral fertilizers and their prices, monopolization of sales; g) Reasons such as insufficient and uneconomic sorting and storage capacities have a negative impact on economic efficiency.

References:

1. “Ўзбекистон Республикасини янада ривожлантириш бўйича Ҳаракатлар стратегияси тўғрисида”. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг Фармони. – Халқ сўзи, 2017 йил 8 февраль.
2. “Ўзбекистон – 2030” Стратегияси тўғрисида. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг Фармони. – Халқ сўзи, 2023 йил 12 сентябрь.
3. Сирожиддинов И. К., Ботирова Р. А. Возможности развития экспорта фруктов и овощей в регионе. – Актуальные вызовы современной науки. Сборник научных трудов. Выпуск 11 (31). Часть И// Переяслав-Хмельницкий, 2018. С. 82 – 85.
4. Сирожиддинов И. Қ., Сирожиддинов К. И. Оппортунитиес фор тхе девелопмент анд инсреасе оф фруит, вегетабле продустион анд тхе экспорт потенциал оф тхе индустрий //Тхеоретисал & Аплиед Ссиенсе. – 2021. – №. 4. – С. 87-90.
5. Qutbiddinovich, S. I., & Abdulazizovich, X. U. B. (2023). GAAP ASOSIGA QO'YILGAN MOLIYAVIY HISOB KONTSEPTSIYALARI. Interpretation and researches, 1(3), 42-50.
6. O'g'li, J. E. S., & Abdulazizovich, X. U. B. (2019). Profits of housekeeping and its development. Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR), 8(4), 419-423.

7. Xolmirzaev, U. B. A., & Madaliev, M. R. (2023). MOLIVIY HISOBOTLARNING QAYTA KO 'RIB CHIQLISHIDA XALQARO TALABLARGA RIOYA ETILISHI ZARURLIGI. Educational research in universal sciences, 2(3), 424-432.
8. Khakimov, B. J., Alimov, B. B., Kholmirezayev, U. A., & Polechov, A. X. (2013). theory of Economic Analysis. Tashkent" economics-finance"—2013.
9. Xolmirzayev, U. A., & Hakimova, G. A. (2023). XO'JALIK YURITUVCHI SUB'EKTlarda DEBITOR QARZLARINING AYLANISHI TAHLILIGA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR: XO'JALIK YURITUVCHI SUB'EKTlarda DEBITOR QARZLARINING AYLANISHI TAHLILIGA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR.
10. Abdulazizovich, K. U. (2023). POSITIVE ASPECTS OF THE CASH METHOD IN SMALL ENTERPRISES UNDER UNUSUAL CIRCUMSTANCES. ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 8.071, 12(11), 38-47.
11. Khakimov, J. B., & Kholmirezayev, A. U. (2021). Positive Aspects Of Cash Method In Small Enterprises In The Context Of Pandemic. Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry, 12(7).
12. Холмирзаев, У. А. (2023). ДЕБИТОР ҚАРЗЛАРИНИ АЙЛАНИШИ ТАХЛИЛИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ МАСАЛАЛАРИ: ДЕБИТОР ҚАРЗЛАРИНИ АЙЛАНИШИ ТАХЛИЛИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ МАСАЛАЛАРИ.
13. Холмирзаев, У. А., & Самижонова, Ш. С. (2022). СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ОТРАЖЕНИЯ ДЕНЕГ В БУХГАЛТЕРСКОМ БАЛАНСЕ. Экономика и социум, (5-2 (92)), 755-766.
14. Холмирзаев, У. А., & Камолдинов, О. О. (2022). АСПЕКТЫ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ ПРЕДСТАВЛЕНИЯ ИНФОРМАЦИИ О ДЕБИТОРСКОЙ ЗАДОЛЖЕННОСТИ ПО ОБОРОТНЫМ СРЕДСТВАМ В БУХГАЛТЕРСКОМ БАЛАНСЕ. Экономика и социум, (5-2 (92)), 767-779.
15. Abdulazizovich, X. U. B. (2024). MOLIVAVIY AKTIVLAR TASNIFINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 41(2), 82-86.
16. Xolmirzayev, U. B., & Ergashev, I. (2024). SANOAT KORXONALARIDA INNOVATION FAOLIYATNI BOSHQARISH TIZIMI. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 3(5), 109-115.
17. Abdulazizovich, X. U. B., & Abdullajanovich, U. T. (2024). SANOAT ISHLAB CHIQRISH KORXONALARIDA INNOVATION FAOLIYAT YO 'NALISHLARI. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 41(5), 17-21.

18. Abdulazizovich, X. U. B. Moliyaviy aktivlar hisobini yuritishda xalqaro standartlar qoidalarini qo'llash masalalari. Ilmiy monografiya. Toshkent-2023.
19. Xolmirzayev, U. B., & Xakimova, G. Z. (2024). SANOAT KORXONALARIDA INNOVATSION FAOLIYATNI AMALGA OSHIRISHNING MOLIVAVIY MEKANIZMI. QO 'QON UNIVERSITETI XABARNOMASI, 10, 96-98.
20. Abdulazizovich, X. U. B., & Muhabbat, N. (2024). INCREASING COMPETITIVENESS IN THE COMMODITY MARKET IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 42(1), 197-206.
21. Gulshirin, J., & Abdulazizovich, X. U. B. (2022, March). INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INVESTMENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF EXPORT DIVERSIFICATION IN THE REGION. In Conference Zone (pp. 277-281).
22. Abdulazizovich, K. U. B. (2023). Improvement Of Information About Accounts Receivable In Current Assets In The Balance Sheet Based On International Standards. Journal of Survey in Fisheries Sciences, 10(2S), 2849-2859.
23. Abdulazizovich, K. U. IMPROVING THE REFLECTION OF MONEY AND CASH EQUIVALENT IN THE ACCOUNTING BALANCE. Dear Academicians & Research Scholars, 55.
24. Abdulazizovich, X. U. B. (2023). XALQARO QOIDALAR ASOSIDA QIMMATLI QOG'OZLAR HISOBINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.
25. Abdulazizovich, K. U. (2022). Improving Methodological Approaches to Financial Asset Accounting. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876, 16(4), 56-62.
26. Холмирзаев, У. А. (2022). ҚИСКА МУДДАТЛИ ҚИММАТЛИ ҚОҒОЗЛАРНИ АНАЛИТИК ҲИСОБИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ. Архив научных исследований, 2(1).
27. Khakimov, B., & Kholmirzayev, U. (2020). Improving Cash Accounting And Analysis On The Basis Of International Experiences. International Finance and Accounting, 2020(1), 18.